

32 Syria is considered one of the richest regions in the world in terms of historical sites and
33 archaeological heritage. Conflicts have caused considerable damage to the Syrian heritage
34 park (Bouvier, 2019).

35 In this context, this study presents results and data of a quantitative monitoring and mapping
36 of the damage in Syria archeological site Apamea, named Afamia in Arabic, on the Orontes
37 River in western Syria. (Figure 1)

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39 (b) (a)
40 Figure 1 (a) Location of the Apamea site in Syria SCR: WGS 84 (b) Limits of the site as proposed by (Balty,
41 2016)

42 43 2. Archeological site Afamia

44 The site of Afamia is located on a limestone plateau in western Syria, near the Orontes
45 River (Al Assi). It is considered to be the seat of a Greco-Roman acropolis, then a
46 medieval citadel (CReA-Patrimoine¹). The city of Apamea is one of the most important
47 cities built in northern Syria during this period. The decade-long conflict in Syria has

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48 had serious consequences for Apamea and its medieval citadel. This site is among the
49 Syrian sites most affected by war damage.

50 These can be direct consequences such as the bombings, or indirect consequences such
51 as the clandestine excavations in Apamea which is located in a border area between the
52 areas controlled by the government and the areas controlled by the opposition. This type
53 of event is often linked to the military occupation of the site and clashes between
54 government forces and armed groups, such as at Qal'at al-Mudiq, a medieval citadel
55 next to the site of Afamia, on the high-altitude zones which were used as military
56 observation posts and which came under artillery fire from the government army after
57 armed rebels took refuge there. Despite this, the site remained under government control
58 during the conflicts period by the presence of many military checkpoints.

59 **3. Method**

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61 In this context, this study aims to show data result from a quantitative monitoring of the
62 damage caused by looting in Afamia during the armed conflict in Syria, using remote sensing
63 and spatial mapping technologies. (Figure 2)

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Figure 2: Methodological scheme

67 **4. Spatial analysis**

68 The spatial analysis of quantitative monitoring is based on an analysis grid covering the
69 entire Apamea site (Balty, 2016) and a large part of the adjacent fields. The analysis grid
70 is subdivided into basic units of 5 meter squares.

71 This dimension of 5m was used based on the dimensions of the holes used for clandestine
72 excavations, dimensions varying between 0.5m and 3.5 meters (Tapete and al. 2016). This
73 choice makes it possible to include and take into account the different sizes of the looting
74 holes.

75 In this context, the database established and analyzed in this study contains 100,000 (exactly
76 98088) spatial record elements, over an area of approximately 2.5 km². The database is
77 associated with this paper.

78 **5. Temporal analysis**

79 This method has been applied over 8 years, starting in 2011, the date of the beginning of the
80 conflicts in Syria. We consider that this 8-year period allows us to study the changes that have
81 taken place in this site and we propose a division into 3 successive periods.

82 2011 (T0), 2012 (T1), 2014 (T2), 2019 (T3) :

- 83 • T0 to T1 (1 year between 2011-2012): period marked by the beginning of the armed conflict
84 and the most intensive looting in the area.
- 85 • T1 to T2 (2 years between 2012-2014): period marked by the continuity of looting,
86 bombardments and artillery fire near the site.
- 87 • T2 to T3 (5 year between 2014-2019): period marked by the continuity of looting and fighting
88 until May 2019

89 **6. Sources of satellite images**

90 Two sources of satellite images were used, images from the SPOT 5 and Pleiades satellites with
91 respective pixel sizes of 10 m and 50 cm.

92 CNES AIRBUS, 2011-07, Apamea Syria, SPOT 5, Maxar Technologies Google Earth, historical
93 imagery. Resolution 2.5 meters

94 - CNES AIRBUS, 2012-04, Apamea Syria, SPOT 5, Maxar Technologies Google Earth, historical
95 imagery. Resolution 2.5 meters

96 The download was made at Google Earth

97 - Pleiades © CNES 2014, Distribution AIRBUS DS, Apamea Syria, Resolution 50 cm
98 DS_PHR1A_201403060825550_FR1_PX_E036N35_0411_01578

99 - Pleiades © CNES 2019, Distribution AIRBUS DS, Apamea Syria, Resolution 50 cm
100 DS_PHR1B_201905040827245_FR1_PX_E036N35_0509_01426

101 These two archive Pleiades images were obtained using Dinamis².
102 Concerning satellite images used in this monitoring study (Figure 3), the SPOT 5 image from
103 2011 before the start of the armed conflict in Syria, another SPOT 5 image from 2012 as well
104 as two Pleiades images from 2014 and 2019 to show the evolution of clandestine excavations.

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109 Figure 3: Satellite images used in this monitoring study: two SPOT 5 images for 2011 and
110 2012 as well as two Pleiades images for 2014 and 2019.

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113 7. Spatio-chronological analysis

114 All data was integrated into a GIS project and processed using QGIS 3.20.3 software
115 A semi-automatic classification was applied to the satellite images based, in the first place, on
116 the visual interpretation, in order to select the learning areas and then automatically classify the
117 content of the SPOT-5 and Pleiades images using the tool Dzetsaka (Karasiak, 2019).
118 In a first step, four classes have been selected:

² Dinamis : the French national facility for institutional procurement of VHR satellite imagery—is a platform that acquires and distributes satellite Earth imagery for French and foreign institutional users under specific subscription conditions. <https://dinamis.data-terra.org>

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- 119 - Site
- 120 - Fields
- 121 - Other: urban areas
- 122 - Illegal excavations

123 Then an additional classification of the images was applied to take into account the previous
 124 state of the pixels as follows:

- 125 • Site without clandestine excavations in T1, T2 and T3
- 126 • Fields without clandestine excavations in T1, T2 and T3
- 127 • Previous clandestine excavations: Clandestine excavations in T-1
- 128 • Recent clandestine excavations: in areas unexcavated in T-1
- 129 • Clandestine excavations erased: Areas already excavated in T-1 in which the excavations no
 130 longer appear.

131 At this stage, a total of 9 categories have been defined (Figure 4).

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134 Figure 4: The categories of classification using in the mapping processes in T0, T1, T2, T3

135 8. Data maps and results

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137 8-year phase (T0-T3): The results of the spatio-chronological analysis obtained using

138 Pleiades and SPOT5 images made it possible to detect clandestine excavations extending over

139 95% of the Apamea site between 2011 and 2019 and over 60% of the adjacent fields, affected

140 by the excavations during this same period (Figure 5 and 6) (Table 1).

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Figure 5 : Map T0 shows the Site Apamea in 2011 before the start of the armed conflict in Syria

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Figure 6 : Map T3 shows the clandestine excavations in the Site Apamea in 2019

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Table 1: Changes of each category between (T0: 2011) (rows) and (T3: 2019) (columns) expressed as a percentage

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2011	Percentage	2019				
		Intact Site	Intact Fields	Traces of former excavations	Previous Clandestine Excavations	Recent Clandestine Excavations
Intact Site	5%		10%	62%	23%	
Intact Fields		40%	13%	26%	21%	
Other						100%

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168 To monitoring and mapping the damage in Syria archeological site Afamia over 8 years the

169 dynamics of the changes were analyzed in three periods (T0/T1, T1/T2 and T2/T3)

170 **Period T0-T1**

171 Over the period T0-T1 (between 2011 and 2012), illegal excavations were detected on 59% of

172 the Apamea site and on 17% of the fields adjacent to the excavated site. (Figure 7) (Table 2).

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Figure 7 : Map T1 shows the clandestine excavations in the Site Apamea in 2012

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186 **Table 2:** Percentage change of each category between (T0: 2011) (rows) and (T1: 2012) (columns) expressed as a
187 percentage

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2011	Percentage	2012		
		Intact site	Intact fields	Clandestine Excavations
Fields			83%	17%
Site		41%		59%

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191 **Period T1-T2**

192 Between 2012 and 2014, illegal excavations involved 42% of the previously unexcavated site

193 as well as 34% of the adjacent fields in the field area that had not been previously excavated

194 (Figure 8) (Table3).

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Figure 8 : Map T2 shows the clandestine excavations in the Site Apamea in 2014

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Table 3: Percentage change of each category between (T0: 2012) (rows) and (T1: 2014) (columns) expressed as a percentage

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	Percentage	2014			
		Intact Site	Intact Fields	Previous Clandestine Excavations	Recent Clandestine Excavations
2012	Intact Site	58%			42%
	Intact Fields		66%		34%
	Clandestine Excavations			100	

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215 **Period T2-T3**

216 Between 2014 and 2019, illegal excavations were detected on 78% of the previously
 217 unexcavated site and 26% of the fields adjacent to the previously unexcavated area (Figure 9)
 218 (Table 4).

229 Figure 9 : Map T3 shows the clandestine excavations in the Site Apamea in 2019

231 **Table 4:** Percentage change of each category between (T2:2014) (rows) and (T3:2019) (columns), expressed as a
 232 percentage

	Percentage	2019				
		Intact Site	Intact Fields	Traces of former excavations	Previous Clandestine Excavations	Recent Clandestine Excavations
2014	Intact Site	22%				78%
	Intact Fields		73%			27%
	Previous Clandestine Excavations			13%	87%	
	Recent Clandestine Excavations			26%	50%	24%

236 **9. Datasets, categories, and supplementary information availability:**

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238 The data associated with our paper is arranged in CSV file.

239 The CSV files (Data-Afamia-MOBAIED) contains 143,426 rows and 9 columns that

240 represent the 143,426 entities (points) which can be projected under an adapted GIS. of which

241 100,000 (exactly 98088) correspond to the archaeological sites according the limits defined by

242 Balty (2016) as shown in Figure.1, those points have value 1 in (Categories 2011).

243 The ID for each entity is specified at the column (A), the spatial coordinates are determined

244 under WGS 84 / UTM zone 37N at the columns (B, C, D, E).

245 The category of each entity is described for each of the years of observation at the columns

246 (F, G, H, I) using the following code:

247 (0) Outside of the archeological site Apamea

248 (1) inside of the archeological site Apamea

249 (2) Fields

250 (3) Other

251 (4) Intact Site

252 (5) Intact Fields

253 (7) Previous Clandestine Excavations

254 (8) Recent Clandestine Excavations

255 (9) Traces of former excavations

256 Creation dates of CSV file: 15/08/2021-31/03/2022

257 Dataset Creators: Samira MOBAIED

258 Language: English

259 License: CC-BY-NC-ND

260 Repository location: ZENODO: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574172> (Mobaied, 2023)

261 Publication date: 21/01/2023

262 **10.Data synthesis**

263 The Apamea site was intensively excavated between 2011 and 2019. The use of high-resolution
264 multi-source satellite images (SPOT 5 with a resolution of 2.5 m and Pleiades with a resolution
265 of 70 cm) is proving to be very effective in detecting the appearance of clandestine excavations
266 and in monitoring the damage caused by these excavations on archaeological sites. The results
267 show that clandestine excavations extending over 95% of the Apamea site between 2011 and
268 2019, as well as over 60% of the adjacent fields affected by the excavations during the same
269 period.

270 Apamea has been investigated and used as a case study for many methods to assess damage and
271 detect looting (Tapete et al., 2016), the model on this paper has the advantage to took into
272 account the previous state of each pixel, according to the diagram explained in Figure 4, we
273 think that is more suitable for monitoring the quantitative damage caused by such excavations
274 in archaeological sites. The data presented in this study can be used to continue monitoring the
275 site concerned, as well as the method used, which can be a long-term monitoring method for
276 this site and also other archaeological sites in the conflict zones.

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279 Authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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281 References

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